

IMPORTANCE OF DIET AND LIFESTYLE MODIFICATION IN PRAMEHA

Dr. Shivanand Shedyal*

Pg Scholar, Baddur Lane Banahatti S/O Gurunath Shedyal Baddur Lane Banahatti Tq-
Rabakavi-Banahatti Dis- Bagalkot, Bagalkote, Karnataka, India.

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*Corresponding Author

Dr. Shivanand Shedyal

Pg Scholar, Baddur Lane Banahatti
S/O Gurunath Shedyal Baddur Lane
Banahatti Tq- Rabakavi-Banahatti Dis-
Bagalkot, Bagalkote, Karnataka, India.

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ABSTRACT

Majority of many chronic diseases relevant today are now being claimed as lifestyle disorders. Ayurveda has potential to preventing lifestyle disorders: prameha is major health problem for the world in the 21st century. The prevalence of prameha is increasing around the world. India has acquired the second position in the list of countries with higher diabetic patients. Lifestyle and eating disorders are becoming the main reason behind the various diseases and diabetes is a lifestyle disorder whose number is increasing at higher space. In Ayurvedic system of medicine for any disease the first line of management is Nidana parivarjana (avoiding the cause) which is the primary step. Internal and external medication is of secondary importance. Prameha (diabetes mellitus) is caused by mithya ahara vihara such as sedentary lifestyle, excessive sleep, excessive intake of curd, meat soups of domestic, aquatic, and

marshy land animals, milk products, freshly harvested food articles, fresh wine, jaggery preparations and all other kapha promoting substances, laziness, intake of food substances which are cold, unctuous, sweet, fatty and liquid. Mostly sedentary mode of life, viruddha and Aahita Aahara (incompatible diets) Ati matra sevana (excessive intake) leads to the dreadful disease called Prameha (diabetes mellitus). prameha is a Tridoshja Vyadhi in which kapha is a pradhana dosha. Bahu and abaddha meda is Pradhan dushya. Prabhut and avil mutrata are main symptoms. Prameha patient advised what they should not have in their diet, but it is very uncommon that they are advised what they should have particular in their diet. Disease specific dietary measures are unique concept of Ayurveda. A properly selected

diet plan and lifestyle modification is important in disease management. pathya for Prameha explained throughout samhita.

KEYWORDS: Prameha, lifestyle effect, Pathya, Apathya, Diabetes Mellitus.

INTRODUCTION

Prameha is a lifestyle disorder which is emerging as a leading cause of for various disabilities and death around the world. As per charak Samhita, prameha is a tridoshaja vyadhi.^[1] The word Prameha means “To flow “which is derived from the Sanskrit root “Mih Sechane”.^[2] Prameha is of 20 types based on dosha predominance, categorised namely as Kaphaja, Pittaja, Vataja Prameha^[3] on the basis of etiology, Sushruta has mentioned clearly two types of Prameha.^[4] Sahaj Prameha (hereditary) and Apathyanimittaja Prameha (Acquired). kapha prakopaka Aahara and Vihara are main causative factors of Prameha.^[5] Prameha is a condition which occurs due to the vitiation of all three doshas and Jala Mahabhoota. Deranged Jala Mahabhoota affects the tissue of the body mainly Muscular and Fatty tissues. This results in hypotonicity and loose consistency of the tissues. Due to aggravation of Kapha dosha and Kleda formation occurs in body resulting into the impaired fat and lipid metabolism. When the excess production of Kleda occurs inside the body, it causes production of cloudy urine in high amount. Excessive formation of Kleda affect the tissues such as of the muscles, fat, lymph etc. and causes Shaithilya.^[6] The chikitsa of prameha explained by Acharya Charak, Sushruta and Vagbhata. Pathya Apathya is the main part of the treatment along with the medicines. Cost effective Ayurveda lifestyle modification can contribute towards preventing and managing the burden of prameha. The study of Aahar and Vihara reveals the rich knowledge of the Ayurveda in the prevention of Parmeha by following lifestyle modification. therefore, it is essential to recognize the potential of the Ayurveda and lifestyle modification and diet plays a first step in the fight against Prameha.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

To study the Role of diet and lifestyle Modification in prameha in detail.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. All the references regarding prameha Diet and lifestyle modification are collected from various Samhitas.
2. Concept of diet and lifestyle modification is studied in detail.

The Trayopstambha mentioned in Ayurveda classics are Aahar, Nidra, Brahmacharya. All these plays very important role in supporting the Trayopstambhas. Aahar is one such supporting pillar whose quality, quantity, compatibility, processing and consumption criteria are considered as an important factor in Ayurveda.^[7] Aahara and Vihara which are suitable for Pramehi are called pathya and those induce Prameha are called Apathya. Ayurveda recognized the importance of food and daily activities in Prameha.

Dietary modification in Prameha.^[8]

Food Type	Pathya	Apathya
Cereals	Adequate Barley, Millet, Wild Millet Less Quantity: Wheat	Rice, processed wheat flour, newly harvested Cereals
Pulses	Adequate Quantity: Bengal gram, Green gram Less Quantity: horse gram, pigeon pea	Black gram, Kidney beans
Vegetables	Adequate Quantity: Patola, Drumstick, leafy vegetables like fenugreek leaves, vegetables with bitter taste predominance like bitter guard Less Quantity: Bottle guard Cauliflower, cabbage	Starchy vegetables. Potato, Yam.
Fats	Less Quantity: mustard oil, flex seed oil, meat of goat and rabbit	Ghee, animal fat, Hydrogenated Ghee, Soyabean oil, Groundnut oil
Kitchen spices	Turmeric, Pippa, Zinger, Garlic, Fenugreek seeds Rock salt	Excessive Mixed spices Coconut paste
Fruits	Adequate Quantity: Indian gooseberry, black berry Moderate quantity: Indian bael, elephants nuts, Guava Less quantity: sweet lemon, unripe papaya and Apple	Ripen Sweet fruits like Mango, Orange, Chiku, Grapes, Banana, Litchi, Ripe Papaya, Pear, Pineapple, Jack fruit,
Drinks	Moderate quantity: Takra, Madhudaka Less Quantity: Skimmed Milk, Tea without Sugar, Black Tea without sugar, black Tea without sugar, Green Tea	Sugarcane Juice, Whole Milk, sweet buttermilk, Curd, Excessive Water, Cold and Freeze Water, Soft cold Drinks, Alcohol
General Guidelines	Increase Low Glycemic Index food in diet, maintain portion control, reduce the quantity of food intake	High Glycerin Index diet, mutton, Eggs, Poultry, butter and Milk products, Desserts like different sweets, Ice-cream

Lifestyle modification in Prameha

Activities	Do's	Don'ts
Sitting	On Stool or Chair without support, on a hard surface, chair, on mat or hard cushion	On a comfortable Sofa, chair with back support, Movable chair, on a soft cushion, watching TV, movies for long hours
Sleeping	On hard bed, Only at Night for 6-8 Hours	On Soft Mattress, Dunlop, Day sleeping, Night sleep for long hours,
Studying	Sitting on Mat and loudly reading	Lying on soft bed or sitting on soft comfortable chair and studying
Physical activity	Increase activity, social activities, Sports, Farming, Gardening, Brisk walking	Sedentary Life Physical activity-sitting or lying for longer duration
Miscellaneous	Walk to work, travel by public vehicle and walk the rest to your work, climb up the stairs	Travel by comfortable luxurious vehicle, use of elevator
Exercise	Brisk walking, jogging, cycling, skipping, Dancing, Swimming	-
Yoga	Aasana like Matsyendraasana, Vajrasana, Pacchimotasana, Pranayama like: Bhramari and Bhastrika, Kapalbhati	-

DISCUSSION

Ayurveda is a science that has given importance to diet and regimen as a part of Chikitsa. Pathya Apathya plays supportive role in the management of Yanya Vyadhi especially like that of Prameha. Prameha occurs due to Tridosha Dushti but Kaphakrut hetu and Kaphadushti are mainly responsible for Dosha Dushti Samurcchana. i.e Samprapti. Acharyas indicated the importance of Pathya Ahara by stating that if a patient takes wholesome food, then there is no need of medicine and if a patient continuously consumes unwholesome food, then also there is no need of medicine. Hence Pathya is key factor in maintaining health. Concept of Pathya changes at every moment and with every individual. What is Pathya to one person may not be Pathya to another person. Even it changes in the same individual depending upon various components like - Age, psychological parameters, Dosha Avastha, Desha, Satmya etc. So, considering and elaborating the diet plan need a lot of attention from the physician. As all the Dosha and Dhatu except Asthi along with Oja are involved in the pathogenesis of Prameha regular pathya sevan is very important. Modification of diet consists of maintenance of proper nutrition and monitoring of calories ingested, individual food sources that make up these calories and the distribution of the calories throughout the day. Attainment of optimum body weight results in marked reduction in hyperglycaemia and increase in target cell response to insulin. for a healthy body we needed to discourage the harmful lifestyle and find

out the high-risk population and make them adopt the real principle of life style through Sadvrittapalana.

CONCLUSION

Ayurveda has explained Nidanpamchak of Prameha in detail. If one can understand the samprapti of Prameha the he can treat the patient in proper way. Prameha is a silent killer having various etiological factors such as Apathya Aahar, Apathya Vihara, Sedentary lifestyle, etc. Treating the disease through medicines is not only cost ineffective but sometimes it has various side effects also. Diet and Lifestyle modifications the best way to prevent the occurrence of the disease and if it has occurred its spread and complications can also be prevented.

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